

STUDIES ON THE SEED CAKE OF *ANNONA SQUAMOSA*. PART II. THE AMINO-ACIDS OF THE CAKE PROTEINS

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The circular paper chromatography of the hydrolysates of the proteins of the seed cake of *A. squamosa* indicates the presence of the leucines, phenylalanine, valine, methionine, tyrosine, proline, alanine, glutamic acid, threonine, aspartic acid, glycine-serine, arginine, histidine, lysine and cystine. The identity of these amino-acids has been confirmed (a) by resorting to specific tests for some of the amino acids, (b) by separating them into basic, dicarboxylic and monoamino-monocarboxylic acids with the aid of ion-exchange resins, and (c) by adopting the mixed chromatography technique.

In the previous communication,¹ it was shown that the seed cake of *A. squamosa* contained about 21% of proteins. Results obtained on analysis of the proteins according to the method of Van Slyke² had also been reported. This analysis, based on the determination of the chemical groups characteristic of the different amino-acids, supplies information mainly on the diamino-acid fraction in the hydrolysate. The identification of the amino-acids of the proteins by applying the technique of partition chromatography on filter paper is described in this communication. The circular paper technique of Rutter³ as modified by Giri and Rao⁴ has been adopted in our experiments. The amino-acids have been identified not only by their relative positions and shades of colour with ninhydrin on the developed chromatogram, but also by specific colour reactions for some of them, and adoption of mixed chromatography technique.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ordinary desiccators (diam. 17cm. and 21cm.) were employed for running the chromatograms, the filter paper circles being held at their periphery between the body and lid of the desiccators. Whatman No. 1 filter paper, obtained as circles or cut into suitable circles from larger sheets, was used as such. The solvent used was a mixture of *n*-butanol-acetic acid and water as recommended by Partridge⁵.

The procedure for spotting the amino-acid solutions for irrigation, marking the boundary and ordinary development (by spraying with 0.1% ninhydrin in acetone) was substantially the same as described by several workers in the field.

Protein hydrolysate.—The protein in the powdered, defatted seed cake (light petroleum extraction) was extracted with 0.3% sodium sulphite solution and precipitated from the extract by passing sulphur dioxide at room temperature. It was hydrolysed by refluxing for 18 to 20 hours with 20% HCl which was later removed by the usual methods. In the hydrolysate, made up to a known volume, nitrogen was estimated by the micro-Kjeldahl method. For identification of tryptophan in the protein, it was hydrolysed by refluxing with 5 N-NaOH for 4 to 5 hours at 110°-125°. The alkali was neutralised with 7N-H₂SO₄ and the solution was made up to a known volume.

For purposes of comparison casein hydrolysates were prepared in the same manner. The hydrolysate volumes were then so adjusted that they contained 5 mg. nitrogen per ml.

Identification of the amino-acids in the cake protein.—The separation of bands in a single-run chromatogram (18.5 cm. paper) of the protein hydrolysate was not complete, in as much as overlapping and diffusion were present. The amino-acids present in greater quantity (e.g. arginine) tended to spread over adjacent bands of amino-acids present in smaller proportion. However, a rough idea of the amino-acid composition of the protein could be obtained even in a single-run chromatogram using a larger filter paper (diam. 25 cm.). It was found better to adopt the multiple development technique⁴ whereby the amino-acids of the protein were found to separate into distinct bands after three developments. Although recourse to R_f values could not be had in the multiple-developed chromatograms for identification of the bands, it was possible to identify the bands clearly, since arginine and proline bands were easily identified (the first by its intensity and position and the second by its yellow colour and position) and from the relative positions of the other bands, they could also be identified. The following bands were thus distinguished (in the ascending order of R_f values): (1) cystine, (2) lysine, (3) histidine, (4) arginine, (5) a band representing glycine-serine-aspartic acid, (6) a band corresponding to glutamic acid-threonine, (7) alanine, (8) proline, (9) tyrosine, (10) valine-methionine, (11) phenylalanine and (12) leucines. The separation of the basic amino-acid bands was complete by this multiple development, although bands 5, 6, 10 etc. could not be completely resolved into individual bands of the component amino-acids.

The identity of the amino-acids (bands) was confirmed, as described below, by running mixed chromatograms by employing specific colour tests, by separating the amino-acids into basic amino-acids and the rest, and by separating them by using ion-exchange resins.

Mixed chromatograms.—The cake hydrolysate was alternated with known mixtures of amino-acids on either side or with casein hydrolysate on one side and a known mixture of amino-acids on the other side, and the chromatograms developed in the usual way⁴. By this means, the individual bands were easily identified. They were also identified by running the cake hydrolysate with the addition of known amino-acids, and comparing the bands in the mixed chromatograms as before. The increase in intensity of the bands, when known amino-acids were added to the cake hydrolysate, served to indicate the presence of those particular amino-acids. For this purpose, the following four mixtures of known amino-acids were used: (1) leucine, methionine, threonine and arginine; (2) isoleucine, tyrosine, aspartic acid and histidine; (3) norleucine, alanine, glycine and lysine; (4) valine, glutamic acid, serine and cystine.

Specific tests.—The identification of the amino-acid bands was further confirmed by the application of specific colour reactions for some of the amino-acids. The circular paper, after drying the solvent, was cut into several sectors (an even number, usually eight), each sector being numbered so that these could later be joined to give a complete circle. Odd-numbered sectors were sprayed with ninhydrin as usual and developed, and the amino-acid bands were marked on them. The other sectors were treated as shown below.

(a) One sector was sprayed with freshly diazotised *p*-bromoaniline⁶, when histidine gave a discernible red colour and tyrosine, a brownish colour. Cystine and two other amino-acids gave a pale yellow colour which, however, faded on keeping overnight.

(b) Another sector was sprayed with platinic iodide (obtained by mixing equal volumes of 0.066*M*-KI and 0.0033*M*-H₂PtCl₆ and diluting to four times the volume). The positions of cystine and methionine were indicated as white or pale yellow bands against a pink background due to the reagent⁷.

(c) A third sector was sprayed with 0.2% isatin in *n*-butanol containing 4% acetic acid⁸. A blue band developed slowly and intensified overnight at the position corresponding with the proline band, but hydroxyproline could not be identified in the chromatogram.

(d) A fourth sector was tested for arginine by the Sakaguchi test by spraying with a 0.1% solution of 2-naphthol in *N*-NaOH and after drying, further spraying with the hypochlorite reagent (prepared by mixing equal volumes of 5% NaOCl and ethanol). A red band corresponding to arginine developed in this sector.

The sectors were reassembled into a whole circle and the amino-acid bands marked in individual sectors were compared and their identities confirmed. For purposes of comparison, the hydrolysate of casein was also subjected to a similar examination by the techniques mentioned above. On a qualitative basis, it was found that the cake protein was richer in cystine,

arginine and alanine as compared with casein and poorer in lysine, proline, tyrosine, valine, methionine and phenylalanine. The intensity of the bands due to other amino-acids was nearly same in the cake-protein hydrolysate and the casein hydrolysate.

Valine.—When the hydrolysate was treated with hydrogen peroxide and then developed; it was found that the valine-methionine band was reduced in intensity, but was distinctly visible, indicating the presence of valine in the hydrolysate. The intensity of the serine-glycine band was enhanced slightly due to the methionine sulphoxide overlapping this band.

Tryptophan.—The presence of the tryptophan band between the bands of tyrosine and valine-methionine was noted in the alkali hydrolysate of the cake protein. This band was not seen in the acid hydrolysate as tryptophan was destroyed during acid hydrolysis.

Phosphotungstic acid precipitation.—The cake-protein hydrolysate was analysed according to the Van Slyke procedure; the P.T.A.-precipitated fractions and the P.T.A.-filtrate fractions were chromatographed. It was noted that the P.T.A. precipitate contained cystine, lysine, histidine and arginine and the other amino-acids were present in the filtrate.

Use of ion-exchange resins.—The protein hydrolysate (2 ml.) containing 10 mg. nitrogen adjusted to p_H 6.8 was shaken for 30 minutes with 400 mg. of Amberlite I.R. 100 resin. The p_H of the liquid fell down to 0.1 and on chromatographing it, it was found that although the basic amino-acid bands were only faintly visible, they were still perceptibly present. The solution was shaken with another 200 mg. of the resin for further 30 minutes at the end of which period, the p_H was nearly 0.0 and the chromatogram showed lysine, histidine and arginine to be completely adsorbed by the resin.

The resin was repeatedly stirred with 5 ml. aliquots of distilled water, till the decanted water was found to be ninhydrin-negative. The resin was then stirred with 1% aqueous pyridine, twice, with 5 c.c. each time. The pyridine extract was free of basic amino-acids.

The adsorbed basic amino-acids were eluted by shaking the resin with 4% ammonium hydroxide. The extract gave strong bands of lysine and arginine and a faint histidine band.

The cation-free protein hydrolysate was evaporated nearly to dryness and then shaken with Amberlite IR-4B. This was washed with distilled water, and the glutamic and aspartic acids were eluted by shaking with 4%

HCl. Both those acids were present in the extract. The monoamino-monocarboxylic acids left after these operations were chromatographed separately and all of the various extracts were run on mixed chromatograms. It was thus shown that (a) the glutamic acid-threonine band contained both glutamic acid and threonine and (b) the aspartic acid-serine-glycine band contained aspartic acid as well as serine-glycine.

The quantitative aspects of this work will be reported later.

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